

An Assessment of the Needs of First Generation College Girls Students

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ABSTRACT

Prevailing social issues make the parents not to send the girl children to the college. They feel if the girl children go for higher studies, there is a chance for delayed marriage. People belong to some society are against to send the girl children to college and also they do not allow them to study in co-education college. There are so many issues regarding the higher education of the first generation college girl's students. Therefore in this study the researcher has made an attempt to find out the level of need of first generation College Girls Students and to identify the difference between the need of first generation first generation College Girls Students based on the select sub samples -Locality of the learners (Urban/Rural), Course of the study (UG/PG), Stream of the study (Arts/Science). For this purpose the researcher has used a sample of 500 first generation college girls students for collecting data. A self structured questionnaire has been used. Collected data have been analyzed with descriptive statistics and t test. The findings of the study indicate that the level of need of first generation College Girls Students is high and there is significant difference of needs between the first generation college girl students of selected subsamples.

KEYWORDS: Generation, College Girls, Learners, Higher Education

INTRODUCTION

First generation women learners have challenges in getting higher education. Parents do not allow their women children to pursue higher level of education. Because they lack of awareness and negative attitude towards higher education. Women are forced to depend on others for their future. But if women are educated, it is helpful to take decisions without depending on others and they lead independent jobs successfully in turn they empower their family also. Based on the view of Manju Khosla (2018), at present, female students and teachers facing many problems that hamper their potential and adversely affect their personal and professional development.

“Education is most powerful weapon that one can use to change the world”. The world of each and every individual starts from its own family. So, it has to give the child a proper environment, situation, sources and all the necessary things as the foundation for her life. Family is the basic and first school, the child should get all needs from the family, and to get values such as respect, security, awareness and encouragement. Being the elder of the family, parents should be supportive and encourage the child. Burden

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of the family is going to be laddered on the eldest child. It is more certain that encouragement, supportive of the family be offered to her by sharing household works and giving guidelines. Financial sources are also considered as the main role to pursue higher studies.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

Reference: Dr. Gurudutta P. Japee, (2019). The purpose of this study is to investigate the state of affairs concerning the most pressing problems facing women in Indian universities today. It will highlight approaches that might aid policymakers and others involved in higher education in their quest to increase women's participation in this field.

Dr. Rumpa Das (2020) The level of education available in a country is indicative of its economic and social progress. The critical thinking skills of today's pupils rely heavily on their exposure to higher education. Women's access to higher education promotes economic growth and social progress at home and abroad. This research aims to (i) examine how well informed women are about higher

education, and (ii) investigate the unique challenges faced by female college students. The only way to make a lasting change in higher education is to dramatically increase the number of women who enrol in and graduate from four-year institutions. Creating and enforcing strong rules and procedures may help abolish discrimination against women in higher education. When women achieve financial autonomy and secure work, they may contribute significantly to the family's financial well-being. An educated woman has the tools, confidence, and influence to make the world a better place. Equal opportunity education may help women realize their full potential and join the ranks of the world's top achievers.

Xi Lin (2016) This research reviews the literature on the obstacles and difficulties faced by women adult students at universities and colleges in the United States. The findings showed the most important factors linked to obstacles and difficulties of this group include commitments with numerous tasks, a lesser degree of self-confidence and inadequate family and social support. Suggestions and consequences of helping this student group are addressed. The aim of this research is to increase awareness of the challenges that women adult students face. It is also anticipated that this particular student group would get greater assistance from family, friends, schools and communities.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM: Very little percentage of women only reaches the level of higher education. This may be due to ignorance of the family. But in society too, there is a social stigma that women has to perform household works rather than giving higher education. Preference is given only to male child for education. To avoid spending money on female child, female infanticide is common earlier. There are a lot of evidences that many policies formed to safeguard and in the upliftment of female or women in the society. Very recently women are facing harassment in work place and in the place of study also. Hence the problem can be rectified by giving proper education (**Jayachandran,2021**). So the researcher has stated the problem as “An Assessment of the Needs of First Generation College Girls Students”

Objectives:

- To find out the level of need of first generation College Girls Students
- To identify the difference between the need of first generation first generation College Girls Students based on the select sub samples -Locality of the learners (Urban/Rural), Course of the study (UG/PG), Stream of the study (Arts/Science).

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

1. The level of need of first generation College Girls Students is high.
2. There is no significant difference between the need of first generation College Girls Students based on the select sub samples.

Methodology:

The population included in the present study are the first generation women learners studying in UG and PG programmes in the academic year 2021-22 in Paschim Medinipur and Purba Medinipur districts of West Bengal. Inorder to carry out the present study the researcher has randomly selected first generation women learners studying in the colleges of Paschim Medinipur and Purba Medinipur districts of West Bengal. The samples of the study included 500 learners from the selected colleges.

The researcher has constructed the questionnaire on need of first generation women learners to collect data from the representative of the population. The item framed was based on the factors of Home, Educational, Psychological and Social. The preliminary form of the questionnaire consisted of 50 items for the variable need with four point sscale (Strongly Agree/Agree/Disagree/Strongly Disagree) and the scoring procedure for the response carries 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively(only positive statements). The obtained data have been analyzed by using the Descriptive Statistics and t test.

Data Analysis:

Table 1-Descriptive Statistics for Needs of first generation College Girls Students

Parameters	Values
N	500
Minimum	56
Maximum	177
Mean	120.332
Median	123
SD	25.2677
SEM	1.1300
Skewness	-0.0489
Kurtosis	2.6524

The above table1 shows the descriptive statistics for the needs of first generation college girls students. It is clear that the calculated mean score is 120.332 with the minimum range of 56 and maximum range of 177. SD score is 25.2677 and the Standard Error Means is 1.1300 with the Kurtosis value 2.6524. The score range for Needs of first generation college students is 45-180. It is evident that the calculated mean score is higher than the mid value 90. Therefore it can be concluded that the level of need of first generation College Girls Students is high. Hence the formulated

hypothesis “The level of need of first generation College Girls Students is high” is accepted.

Table 2-Difference between the need of first generation first generation College Girls Students based on Locality of the Learners

Group	N	Mean	SD	SEM	df	t
Rural	360	121.0527	25.3909	1.338218	498	1.0229
Urban	140	118.4785	24.9423	2.108009		

To find the significant difference between the two sub-groups regarding the needs of first generation college girls students on the basis of Locality of Learners the ‘t’ value has been calculated. The table 2 shows that the mean score of needs for rural girls students is 121.0527 and SD is 25.3909. On the other hand the mean score of the needs for Urban girls students is 118.4785 and SD is 24.9423. It is found from the above table that the calculated ‘t’ value 1.0229 is found to be not significant. Hence the research null hypothesis is rejected and it is concluded that there is significant difference of needs between the college girl students of Rural and Urban.

Fig. Showing Difference between the need of first generation first generation College Girls Students based on Locality of the Learners

Table 3-Difference between the need of first generation first generation College Girls Students based on Course of the Study

Group	N	Mean	SD	SEM	df	t
UG	285	120.6561	25.1051	1.487098	498	0.3300
PG	215	119.9023	25.5340	1.741404		

To find the significant difference between the two sub-groups regarding the needs of first generation college girls students on the basis of Course of the Study the ‘t’ value has been calculated. The table 3 shows that the mean score of needs for UG girls students is 120.6561 and SD is 25.1051. On the other hand the mean score of the needs for PG girls

students is 119.9023 and SD is 25.5340. It is found from the above table that the calculated ‘t’ value 0.3300 is found to be not significant. Hence the research null hypothesis is rejected and it is concluded that there is significant difference of needs between the college girl students of UG and PG.

Table 4-Difference between the need of first generation first generation College Girls Students based on Steam of the Study

Group	N	Mean	SD	SEM	df	t
Arts	310	120.7161	26.1805	1.486952	498	0.4339
Science	190	119.7052	23.7575	1.723550		

To find the significant difference between the two sub-groups regarding the needs of first generation college girls students on the basis of Steam of the Study the ‘t’ value has been calculated. The table 4 shows that the mean score of needs for Arts girls students is 120.7161 and SD is 26.1805. On the other hand the mean score of the needs for Science girls students is 119.7052 and SD is 23.7575. It is found from the above table that the calculated ‘t’ value 0.4339 is found to be not significant. Hence the research null hypothesis is rejected and it is concluded that there is significant difference of needs between the college girl students of Arts and Science.

Findings:

1. The level of need of first generation College Girls Students is high
2. There is significant difference of needs between the college girl students of Rural and Urban.
3. There is significant difference of needs between the college girl students of UG and PG.
4. There is significant difference of needs between the college girl students of Arts and Science

Conclusion:

The findings of this research have shed some insight on the obstacles that women face while pursuing higher education. According to the findings, the women do confront significant obstacles throughout their academic pursuits, but they are by no means insurmountable. The consequence is that the project has to be redirected and improved so that it attracts and serves its intended demographic more effectively. The researcher has some recommendations for him to consider.

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